
THE ETYMOLOGY OF MINERALOGICAL TERMS AND THEIR STYLISTIC CHARACTERISTICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract

This article examines the semantic meaning of mineral units and the language layer to which they belong. The stylistic characteristics of the names of precious stones and ores in literary works written in Uzbek and English are also covered in detail in the article.

Keywords

mineralogical terms, linguistics, semantic feature, stylistic meaning, figurativeness

The study of the names of precious stones and ores contributes to the understanding of how language and culture intersect. By analyzing the linguistic aspects of these names, researchers can unravel the intricate relationship between language and the natural world. This analysis provides insights into how different cultures perceive and name minerals, reflecting their unique perspectives and beliefs.

Currently, more than 2,000 minerals are known to science. The field of mineralogy that studies precious stones is called "edelsteinkunde". Its international name is gemology (from Latin "gemma" meaning "semiprecious stone"; from English "gem" meaning "precious stone").[1] One of the key problems facing the area of linguistics is the insufficient scientific examination of the history of the formation of mineral names and their meanings.

We were sure that there exist lexical units associated with a foreign language layer when we examined the names of precious stones and ores. It is well known that, the majority of technical and scientific terminology have Greek or Latin roots. Even in the process of analyzing the etymology of the names of precious stones and ores, we have witnessed that most of these terms are borrowed. In particular, the names of mineralogical units in English lexicology are borrowed from Greek (diamond, chlorite, beryl, graphite), Latin (muscovite, garnet, sulfure, opal), French

(turquoise, biotite), German (goethite, quartz), Arabic (talc, borax), Persian (azurite, cinnabar) and Spanish (*platinum*) languages.[2]

Based on the results of our research, it is worth noting that only a few names of minerals originated from the original English words. In particular, if we look at the etymology of stone names like "gold" and "silver", then, according to some sources, the word "gold" began to be used in writing from about 725, and this word refers to the Old English language and means "yellow".[3] Other sources, however, write that "gold" comes from the German word "gulba", belonging to the Indo-European family of languages.

"seolfor" or "siolfor" are old English words that are variants of the modern word "silver", which, in turn, originated from the German word "silubra", belonging to the Indo-European family. We can say that the meaning of the word "silver" is still remaining unknown to science.

As already mentioned, most of the names of precious stones and ores in English come from other languages. For example, the stone "*amethyst*" originated from the Greek word *amethystos* meaning "*not drunk*" in ancient Greek. Amethyst has also been said to maintain its user sharp-witted and rational. Amethysts are said to increase intelligence and shield against negative thoughts, according to famous inventor and artist Leonardo da Vinci. Also, the word "*rhodolite*" originates from the Greek word meaning "*rose*." A pink gem is known as rhodolite. *Malachite* got its name from the vivid green herb known as mallow in Greek. Bright green bars of gemstone called malachite may be seen running through it. *Kyanite*, a stunning blue gemstone, is named after the Greek word for blue, kyanos. [4]

The name "*citrine*" is derived from the Latin word for "*lemon*," so it should come as no surprise that this sunny, golden stone has long been revered as a healing crystal that provides happiness, good health, vitality, luck, and prosperity

We made an effort to present various mineral names' origins and their semantic meaning as tables as much as we could:

<i>Mineral</i>	<i>Name origin (language)</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
gypsum	gypos (Greek)	plaster
anhydrite	anhydros (Greek)	without water
barite	barus (Greek)	heavy
celestite	coelestis (Greek)	celestial
hematite	aematitis lithos (Greek)	blood stone
borax	bauraq (Arabic)	white
corundum	kuruvinda (Sanskrit)	ruby
pyrite	pyr (Greek)	fire
cinnabar	zinjifrah (Persian)	lost

cryolite	krúos, líthos (Greek)	ice-stone
fluorite	fluere (Latin)	to flow
halite	háls (Greek)	sea
calcite	calx (Latin)	lime
siderite	sideros (Greek)	iron
malachite	molochitus (Greek)	mallows
azurite	lazhward (Persian)	blue
olivine	öliva (greek)	olive fruit
garnet	granatum (Latin)	pomegranate
apatite	apataō (Greek)	deceptive
hydroxyapatite	apatao, hydro- (Greek)	deceptive, water-rich
turquoise	turques (French)	turkish
gold	gold (Old English)	yellow
copper	kyprios (Greek)	of Cyprus
silver	seolfor (Old English)	[meaning unknown/lost]

We are all aware that every word in the English language has a specific meaning, but only words that express concepts have lexical meanings. There are various categories of lexical meaning, such as primary and derived meaning, nominative and figurative meaning, basic meaning, and subordinate meaning. Considering the explanation of the term "mineral" in the Uzbek and English language explanatory dictionary:

MA'DAN-kon, yerosti boyliklari; metal 1. mineral 2. metal 3. ruda

Mineral - 1. a valuable or useful chemical substance that is formed naturally in the ground 2. a chemical that your body needs to stay healthy.

As you can see, in both languages, the main meaning of the word "mineral" is "subsoil, metal". During the analysis of English and Uzbek literary texts, we noticed that the names of precious stones and ores were used not only in the meaning of "rare metal", but also in the meaning of "wealth, youth, beauty, bravery, and courage" and other semantic meanings. In the literary text, you can see that writers used the names of precious stones and ores in a figurative sense to give words a special expressiveness.

There are many examples of how language is used to convey metaphorical meaning. The basis of transfers is a comparison of two things or concepts, i.e. based on a certain connection between two things or concepts (for example, similarity, community, kinship), the name of one of them is transferred to the other to enhance imagery, expressiveness, and accuracy.

The means of artistic representation acquire an emotionally expressive coloring in almost all the main cases in speech. From the means of artistic representation involving the names of precious stones in English and Uzbek oral and written texts, many examples of metaphors, similes, irony, and epithets can be cited. The scope of epithets-adjectives involving the names of precious stones and ores is quite wide in both languages. While "diamond eyes", "sapphire-Tinted skies", "the chrysolite of sunrise", "crystal eyes", "crystal tears", "silver-haired", "golden hair", "golden sun", "golden years", "Emerald Island", "emerald meadows" etc. are frequently observed in English literary texts; "gavhar ko'zlar", "marvariddek tishlar", "feruza osmon", "olmos ko'zlar", "marjondek lablar" are common phrases in the Uzbek texts. It can be observed that the adjective in these combinations served as a figurative description of the properties inherent in a thing, phenomenon, or concept. An adjective is not just a means of decorating a sentence or phrase, it is connected with the content and manifests itself in logical, psychological, linguistic, and literary aspects of speech.

Using the names of precious stones in a metaphorical sense, writers were able to create beautiful examples of expressive, figurative speech in their works.

One of the stylistic devices in which the names of precious stones are involved is an analogy. An analogy is similar to metaphors in that it is built on a figurative meaning by which a person and a subject are compared with each other, but unlike metaphors, in the Uzbek language such means as *-dek, -day, -simon, -namo, kabi, singari, misoli, o'xshash* are used. In English, this stylistic device is called "simile", and in this case, such means like, *as...as, as, and like* are used.

For example:

"O'tgan kunlar" – o'zbek adabiyoti gavhari (metaphor)

"O'tgan kunlar" – bamisoli gavhar (comparison)

Or:

A princess without pearls. (metaphor)

"A princess was like a pearl" (simile)

"eyes like carbuncles", "voice like a bell of Silver", "she is like a pearl", "seas like sapphire", "lips like a ruby", and "eyes like diamonds" are vivid examples of similes that are formed with the names of precious stone.

The English writer Shakespeare skillfully used irony "Upon her nose, all o'er embellished with rubies, carbuncles, sapphires" in "Comedy of Errors" [5]. To describe the shortcomings of the hero's face, the writer turns to precious stones, that is, portrays the shortcomings with something beautiful. It was these precious stones

that the writer chose to accurately express the shape, hardness, and color of acne on Nel's face, beard and managed to awaken the reader's imagination.

As can be seen from the above examples, stylistic devices involving the names of precious stones and ores make our speech touching and attractive. It also demonstrates a writer or speaker's artistic and aesthetic abilities in front of the reader and the audience.

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